

USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS THROUGH TEACHING LANGUAGE

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***Abstract.** The aim of this current article is to expose students to highly engaging opportunities to practice English, using authentic materials is an excellent option that underpin them and the benefits that still might possibly accrue from experimenting with them. Teachers' perspectives of the use of authentic materials in learning and teaching. Furthermore, it also explores some obstacles of using the material.*

***Key words:** educators work, instructions recourse, consideration, summative tasks, itinerary.*

INTRODUCTION

In the fast pace of the world the teaching system is developing in a rapid way. The use of authentic materials are an excellent recourse in any teaching context. Sometimes educators work at institutions that provide lots of materials, while others may only provide a few or none at all. How to incorporate authentic materials depends on each teacher's preference and teaching situation. Materials can supplement an existing curriculum or textbook or can even serve as the basis for an entire course.

We think about authentic materials as any materials that use language to communicate information and meaning (Thomas 2014). This description opens up a wealth of possible resources, most of which are free and easily accessible on the internet or perhaps in our everyday lives.

Uzbekistan has expended effort, money and time, to provide new technologies to schools. As a result there is an opportunity to use authentic materials at schools and other education establishments. Many Uzbek researchers have been interested in studying the importance of using new methods in education.

Using authentic materials can have benefits and challenges just like any other instructional resource. However, with careful consideration, educators can find materials that benefit students and minimize potential difficulties.

What are authentic materials?

One description of authentic materials says that their purpose is to communicate meaning and information and that they are produced for real communication rather than to teach language (Thomas, 2014). Authentic materials for the English language classroom are often free and very easy to find online or perhaps in certain location in your communities. Here are some examples:

-Tv shows, news, segments, documentaries, movie clips and trailers, online videos, and commercials

-Radio broadcasts, songs, and podcasts

-Photographs, artwork, signs, postcards, maps, and advertisement

-Magazines, letters and e-mails, news articles, brochures, websites, blogs and social media posts

- Recipes, food labels, bus and train schedules menus, and price tags and product descriptions

Benefits and challenges of using authentic materials

Authentic materials are beneficial because they show a real -world use of language and often present content that is of high interest to students. Most authentic materials present current topics in news or culture or help students learn information that is useful everyday lives. For this reason, using authentic materials often increases students' motivation and willingness to take risks with English.

Real materials, unlike materials made specifically for teaching ,are not created with certain grammatical structures or vocabulary in mind.

Instead they provide an opportunity for students to read or hear language as it is used in a real -life situation, this can help advance students' language learning by exposing them to new vocabulary and grammatical concepts in a meaningful way.

There are possible challenges when using authentic materials for English instruction .Some time-dependent resources like news stories or social media posts can quickly become outdated.

Although these items may not be useful at a later time. Some materials can pose a challenge, for beginner or even intermediate students. English language learners may have trouble with vocabulary and grammar structures in materials created for a fluent audience, To address this challenge, teachers have to plan thoughtful ways for students to interact with these materials.

Developing tasks to help students demonstrate what they have learned

Authentic materials allow students to demonstrate learning through a wide variety of summative tasks. Summative tasks require that students show their understanding of a unit of study or series of learning activities. Often these tasks can be very creative and engaging because they allow students to demonstrate learning in a meaningful context.

Remember that the goal of using authentic materials is not to memorize vocabulary or language structures but to be able to use new words and language in an authentic way. So rather than giving students a traditional vocabulary quiz on the words they learned in a travel brochure, you might ask that they give a presentation that contains some of the new words. Instead of answering multiple choice comprehension questions about the events in a news story, students might have to write a one-minute radio broadcast blurb that tells the highlights from the story. Below are some ideas for summative tasks that can be used for this purpose after students have had a chance to interact with authentic materials.

A skit containing specific language structures or vocabulary

A film poster advertising a movie or documentary with a tagline that hints at the main problem or event, illustrations or photos of important people, and a visual representation of the setting

A song or poem that contains certain vocabulary or grammatical structures and connects to the topic of the material used in the lesson

A brief TV or radio news broadcast summarizing important events or issues from a news article, video, or blog post

A presentation discussing key points or information learned

An itinerary for a day out to visit at least five different places in the city with bus numbers, stops, and times

A speech taking a position and justifying it with information from the materials

A letter to the newspaper, a lawmaker, or an historical figure

When planning these summative tasks, it is important to have the requirements for students in mind and to communicate them clearly beforehand. For example, if you want your students to be able to plan a day out in the city using a map and a bus schedule, be specific about what time the day should start and end, how many places they need to visit, and what the itinerary should look like. If you expect students to be able to use weather vocabulary and the future tense properly to discuss the forecast for the next five days, students should know how many vocabulary words and what language structures they need to use.

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